

Veligura O.

ORCID ID <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-3904-664X>

Specialist in educational methods
of the form piano and solo singing of the Communal institution
«Semenivka children's music school» in Chernihiv region
(Semenivka, Ukraine) E-mail: helen.ve1983@gmail.com

THE INTRODUCTION OF THE METHODS FOR THE FORMATION SINGING SKILLS OF THE CHILDREN OF JUNIOR SCHOOL AGE AND THE PRESCHOOLERS ON THE PRINCIPLE OF CONTINUITY

The article is devoted to the problem of the continuity of forming singing skills of the children of the determination of preschool and general secondary education. Determined that the forming singing potential of the children the primary link, that conceived in the preschool age and receiving from now on the realization in the junior school age. In this context, the topicality has the ensuring of the pedagogical conditions, the methods, the methodical approaches and the elements of the training for the introduction of the progressive line of the development of the singing skills on the basic principle continuity.

The article's purpose is the elaboration, theoretical substantiation and the experimental testing of the methods` formation of the singing skills of the children of the junior school age and the preschoolers, taking into account the principle of the continuity and the results of the determination the state of this phenomenon.

The methodological base of the investigation was: the state document «National Strategy and Development of Education in Ukraine for 2012-2021», the leading aspects of the methodic of the vocal and the choral work with the children (O. Apraksina, O. Borisova, K. Malinina); the main positions of the peculiarities of the structure of the children's vocal device (N. Hontarenko, L. Dmitriev, A. Menabeni, M. Mikisha, V. Morozov, Yu. Yutsevich, V. Yushmanov); the main principles of the age-specific peculiarities of the development of the psyche of the preschoolers (O. Kononko, V. Kuzmenko) and the children of the junior school age (L. Wenger, M. Zabrotskiy, V. Kuzmenko, V. Kutishenko).

The scientific novelty is in that:

– firstly, the problem of continuity is considered in the formation of the singing skills of the pupils is the primary link of the institutions of general secondary education and the preschoolers; made the integrated methods in this direction;

– secondly, an integrated step-by-step methodology has been developed from the outlined direction; a set of practical tasks has been created, among them the obligatory is the methodical approach «singing in the drawings» in order to determine the state of forming singing skills of the pupils of 1-4 forms and the preschoolers; we also developed test assignments, questionnaires for determining the level of development of singing reflexion of the pupils of the primary link of the institution of general secondary institution;

– the concept of «singing reflexion» was introduced into scientific circulation.

The experiment was carried out on the basis of the Preschool Education № 6 «Sonechko» of the Semenivsky City Council of Chernihiv region and Semenivka gymnasium №2 of Semenivka district council of Chernihiv region.

The molding experiment was carried out from September of the 2012 year to May of the 2015 year. There were 279 contestants in the experiment. They were distributed into two groups: the experimental (147 respondents) and control (132 kids). To the experimental came 89 preschoolers and 58 the children of the junior school age of Gymnasium №2, to control – 74 pupils of the introductions of the pre-school education and 58 junior pupils of Gymnasium №2.

The article presents the author's methodical model. It was introduced in the educational process with the experimental group. Three stages of the experiment were discovered: goal-setting, mobilizing, summarizing. Among the used of the methods and the methodical approaches: the practical tasks of singing, interviewing, questioning, testing and questioning.

Also, are presented the effective methods and the methodical approaches: the singing in the drawings, the explanatory-illustrative (informational-receptive) and the heuristic (partially search) methods and the methodical approach «singing in the drawings». Determined of the state of the results of the introduction the methods with the forming of the singing skills of the children of the junior school age and the pre-school children.

Conclusions. As a result of the molding experiment, we discovered that significant development of singing reflection was observed in pupils of the third and fourth forms. The outlined phenomenon is connected with the deepening and the expansion of knowledge and the skills in comparison with the pupils of the first and second forms. During the experimental research, we found that preschoolers are not able to evaluate independently their own singing yet. Because they have not experience. We have determined that this phenomenon is a newborn in the children of 6 years of age.

The collectives of the experimental and the control groups were happy to fulfill the training tasks, the music teachers of the institutions of general secondary education provided the assistance in creating a good positive microclimate in the classes, and continued to work out our practical tasks for singing, interviewing, questioning, testing and questioning. The music teachers in the work with the EG were to able observe a high interest in performing vocal exercises «singing in the drawings», the songs, some exercises from the course of video tutorials on the Internet portal «Youtube», increased emotional the attitude to singing activity.

Key words: continuity, singing skills, singing reflexion.

Formulation of the problem in general aspect and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. At the present stage of development of education in Ukraine, the formation of singing potential for elementary school students, which is born in preschool children, becomes more important in the younger school age. In this context, the relevance is to ensure the pedagogical conditions, methods, techniques and elements of learning to introduce a gradual development of singing skills and skills based on the principle of continuity. The implementation of such a process should take place through the implementation of the tasks of primary school education as envisaged in the «Draft National Strategy and Development of Education in Ukraine for 2012-2021» and stated that urgent problems are needed, in particular, the implementation of the continuity of education, which will ensure the organizational and content unity, continuity and interconnection of all its parts.

The modern scientists have different determination of mentioned phenomenon. A. Bohush thinking the realization of continuity in the methods, content of training and the forms of the educational work and the introduction educational programs [1]. T. Chala determined the continuity as the ensuring of the incessant education take into account the of reliable age and like the perspective of the development personality[2, c. 6].

The work relevance. Today the problem of the introduction of continuity in elaboration of the educational process of singing is relevant, so that through the educational programs of the institutions of preschool and the primary link of general secondary education take into account tenderness and the malfunction of the child's vocal system and provided for the formation of singing skills from simple to complex through their gradual accumulation and improvement at all stages of learning.

An analysis of main investigations and the publications of the taking problem. The problem of continuity of musical education for preschoolers and junior pupils is multifaceted. It involves specifying the educational problems. For this reason, we investigated the problem in various aspects, namely: the state documents on the strategy for the development of artistic education in Ukraine were considered; the technique of the vocal and the choral work with the children was studied (O. Apraksina, O. Borisova, K. Malinina); the issues of the structure of the children's vocal device (N. Hontarenko, L. Dmitriev, A. Menabeni, M. Mikisha, V. Morozov, Yu. Yutsevich, V. Yushmanov); the issue of the age-specific peculiarities of the development of the psyche of the preschoolers (O. Kononko, V. Kuzmenko) and the children of the junior school age (L. Wenger, M. Zabrotskiy, V. Kuzmenko, V. Kutishenko); discovered the basis of the continuity (A. Bohush, T. Chala, L. Lunyaka, T. Phorostyuk, L. Poryadchenko).

The analysis of the scientific and the methodological literature, of the educational programs on the subject «Music» of the institutions of the secondary general education and the programs of the institutions of preschool education showed that there is still no principle of the continuity in the forming of the singing skills among the junior pupils and preschoolers. There is also no similar the methodological system for the forming of the above-mentioned phenomenon and has not been introduced into these educational institutions.

Formulation of purpose of the article. Present the introduction of the methods for the forming of the singing skills of the children of the junior school age and the preschoolers on the principle of continuity.

Throw lighting of the procedure of the experimental investigation with allusion of the methods' investigation. For solving the tasks in the work were applied the theoretical methods of investigation – analytics for studying theoretical aspects of the problem, comparison, simulation of pedagogical experiment, logical methods of generalization of the received data; the empirical methods – diagnostic (pedagogical observation, conversations; practical tasks) to determine the levels of the forming respondent's singing skills; questioning, testing, interviewing – to determine the level of development of the reflexion of singing of the pupils of the primary link of the institution general secondary education; the pedagogical experiment (molding).

Also there was used a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results of the molding experiment in order to test the effectiveness of developed and tested methods; the methods of mathematical statistics that allowed to carry out quantitative analysis of the results of the molding experiment.

An outline of the main material of investigation with the substantiation of the received of the scientific results. The experimental work on the forming singing skills (molding experiment) was carried out on

the basis of the institution of preschool education № 6 «Sonechko» of the Semenivsky City Council of Chernihiv region and Semenivka gymnasium № 2 of Semenivka district council of Chernihiv region. There were 279 contestants in the experiment. They were divided into two groups: experimental (147 respondents) and control (132 pupils). Such number of pupils allowed us to have reliable data in the process of the pedagogical experiment, taking into account the proportionality.

Of these, 89 preschoolers and 58 the children of the junior school age were enrolled into the pilot, up to 74 pupils of the preschool educational institutions and 58 junior pupils. With the experimental group the educational process took place according to the author's methodical model, with the control – according to the traditional system. In general, the molding experiment took place from September 2012 to May 2015 year. The formative experiment was conducted in three stages:

- goal-setting (September 2012 – May 2013),
- mobilizing (September 2013 – May 2014),
- summarizing (September 2014 – May 2015).

In order to ensure of the mobility of the educational process, we have been developed and approved by the methodologists or the directorate of the educational institutions for the plans of pupils for 2012-2013 academic year, 2013-2014, and 2014-2015. In the older groups «The flower», «The swallow», «The periwinkle», «The fairy-tale» and «The bell» and the pupils of primary school of Semenivka gymnasium № 2 of Semenivka district council of Chernihiv region. In total, 534 children, 4 music teachers of the preschool establishments, 13 educators and 3 teachers of musical art of the institutions of secondary general education were involved in the scientific-pedagogical experiment. Such a large selection of respondents allowed us to obtain reliable data to verify the effectiveness of the developed methods.

In our investigation, we combine three ways of perception: kinetics, visibility and audibility, as respondents simultaneously contemplate drawing, verbal explanation and demonstration of a teacher or music director, and direct movements of hands with hands. In our opinion, such a proposed model for singing small children will have a high impact, since the presented material is understandable and accessible to every child.

To perform such exercises is necessary as with the whole group together, both in subgroups and individually. This person-oriented approach has allowed us to reveal the uniqueness and individuality of the voice of each child, to improve her singing opportunities, to pick up an individual repertoire.

In the course of an experimental research, we found that in the children of six years of age is a newborn. We determined it as the singing reflection. For this reason, the level of development of the singing reflection was measured only by the children of the primary link Semenivka Gymnasium № 2. The singing reflexion is the ability to compare to sing present with the singing in the past.

The heuristic (partially exploratory) method we used to develop the reflexion of singing. The children of the junior of the school age expressed their thoughts, compared the sound quality, singing the main ways of listening, and so on. So, in the work, the pupils were in search of the dynamics, the pace, the character of sound, analyzed the methods of the sound-proofing, the clarity of the dictation and the articulation skills, listened to the intonation and tried to determine its conformity, the accuracy, or vice versa – the detonation, etc. The explicit method provided the development of the ability to distinguish the sound dynamics, the sound modes (*legato*, *leggiero legato*, *non legato*, *staccato*, *marcato*), and others like that. We used it at work with only the children outlined age category.

In the first stage (goal-setting) we was provided the educational programs by training the pre-school educational institution (nursery №6) «Sonechko» of the Commune «Semenivka City Council» of the Chernihiv region, Semenivka Gymnasium №2 of the Semenivka district council of the Chernihiv region for the convenience of the trained, promisingly planned, systematic formation of the phenomenon of dissertation research. Afterwards, we did to rearrange and to replace the methods among themselves, without modifying them and approaches. In particular, we have been widely used the methodical approach – «singing in the drawings».

At the first stage of the molding experiment, we did not measure the degree of development of epy singing reflection, but only on the second (mobilizing) and third (generalizing) stages, as it took us time to provide respondents with the relevant knowledge, the abilities and the skills of the singing so that they could successfully to evaluate their own performances actions.

At the stage of goal-setting we used the explanatory-illustrative (informational-receptive) and the heuristic (partially search) methods, used the explanatory and illustrative, the music director or music teacher explained and told children, demonstrated the correspondence of the vocal sound, methods of sound production. The respondents tried to repeat the exercises, the sermons, performances, and the small songs at the show of a music teacher or a music director.

Analysis of the methodical literature from psychology proved that the children outlined age categories have the visually figurative thinking. Therefore the visuality became the leading line of our investigation. The methodical approach «singing in the drawings» made it possible for us in full volume found the levels of forming singing skills in the preschoolers and the children of the junior school age. Using the methodical approach of «singing in the pictures», the children showed great interest, faithfully performed all vocal exercises.

To form singing skills we used the exercises among which are: «the hissing kittens» (the drawing of a kitten): the children bearing the longer sound «sh» by breathing, loudly or low. «The cats' murmuring» (the drawing of the cats): on the methods of the sound-proofing *legato* in the high leveled movement on the small

tertsia. They connected the sound «u» with the sound «r». «The cooling tea» (the picture of a cup with a spoon): the teacher gave the children wooden sticks and they did these things (the circle movements and simultaneously singing any vowel sounds on the methods of sound production legato in the interval correlation of the second, tertsia, quart, quint. In the work with the preschoolers it is better to use the first two intervals. On the words «blowing the spoon» the children must hold up the wooden sticks to the mouth and blow on them. «Kittens' stretching» (the picture of kittens): the children raise their hands, stretch and enjoy yawning. «Mother's kiss» (the picture of the lips): the children do the kiss of lips. «The lips»: the preschoolers do slightly biting upper and low lips. «An apple» (or «an orange»): the children do first and keep to the mouth. They pronounce actively all vowel sounds. After that they pronounce sounds: «ye» «ya» «yo» «yi». «Stepped pyramid» (the drawing of Chefred's pyramid): the children sing one vowel «i», «a», «o», «u» or «e» on the small league in that succession: I-III, III-IV, IV-V, V-IV, IV-III, III-II, II-I. «The musical hiding-places» (the drawing of the ball over the hiding-places): the children raise their hands forward and do the sharp movements up and down, sing on staccato different vowel sounds on one intonation, after that they do the movements up and down, to change sonority. «To blow on the snowflake» or «to blow on autumn leaf» (the picture of the snowflake on the palm, or the autumn leaf on the palm): the preschoolers raise their palms in front of themselves and blow. They imagine the snowflakes or the leaves. «Awake the cock» (the picture of the cock): the preschoolers must detach to exclaim the sounds «e», «e», «e». «Car wash» (the drawing with the sign of car wash). The teacher says «clean the dust on the car» the children do circle movements by hands saying the sounds «r», «r», «r»; on the words «blowing the dust from the car», they must get air into their lungs and to blow out. On words «to wash a car», they raise their right hand and bear the longer sound «psh». Exercise «high way» (the picture with the sign of highway): the respondents do the palms in front of themselves and up right hand on the sound «u», «o», «^», and left hand down. Why left hand up, they put down their right hand and singing vowel sound «e». Exercise «cuckoo» (the drawing of cuckoo): the children sing the big tertsia down using the method of sound model is legato and staccato on the syllable «cu», «ckoo». «The ancient clock» (the drawing of clock): on the words «wind up the clock» the respondents doing the movements with the right hand and they turn the key and say «kr», «kr», «kr». They do it on the words «unlock the house». On the words «go the clock's hand» they click their tongues. Fast repositioning of the pointer on the flowers shown – the respondents sing the melodic line using the methods of the sound-proofing – staccato for piano accompaniment; they point to the waterfall singing loudly and they show a baby – using of legato on a quiet dynamics (piano). «The field of tulips»: the preschoolers connect get their palms together their palms of hands that of fingers of left and right hands connecting (thumb with the thumb, index finger with the index finger, middle finger with the middle finger, ring finger with the ring finger, pinky with the pinky) and also we connect the inner side of the palms. Separating all fingers together – inhaling, connecting – children breathe out.

We also do the exercises «the carriage ambulance», «the violinist», «the doll», «sowing of pea» «the snake», «refrigerator», «tigers' stretching», «the sun is rising», «a beetle», «a chewing gum», «touch-lost», «the talk», «a dragon», «the merry-go-round», «ts, ts, ts», «catch the drop», «the ball», «downpour», «storm» and many others.

The second stage (mobilizing) allowed mobilizing of the educational process, to select of the effective methods and the methodical approaches for the children, to select the accessible repertoire that corresponds to the specified age category of children and reveals their vocal capabilities in full.

In the third stage of the molding experiment (generalizing), we generalized of the proposed methods for the formation of the phenomenon's investigate.

We directed the educational process in search of new, effective methods, pedagogical decisions and educational elements, taking into account the individual psycho physiological peculiarities of pupils through the reflection of the use of methods and the methodical approaches of training. Provided the formation of the singing skills and the development of the reflection of singing through the introduction of advanced methods (using online resources – video tutorials on vocal on the portal Youtube). We was determined the level of development of the reflection of singing by oral questioning after inclusion on the multimedia whiteboard video tutorials from the outlined portal.

So, we used the methods for to determine the level of the development of the reflection of singing and in order to understand the subjects of self-worth studying performances – interviews, questionnaires, and tests.

The results of investigation. As a result of the implemented methods for the development of the reflection of singing, it was found that pupils of the third and fourth forms have a high degree of development. In our opinion, the result is gaining more experience, the knowledge, the skills and the abilities compared to the first and second forms. The following factors influence: the availability of a certain degree of development of the musical abilities, greater development of the attention and ability to analyze, and the levels of formation of the singing skills in the experimental and the control groups are presented in quantitative and percentage indicators. The results presented in the table № 1, № 2, № 3.

Table 1

The results of the experimental investigation for the forming singing skills and the development of reflection of singing in the pupils of junior school age (116 children)

Levels	KG	KG	EG	EG
	number	%	number	%
High (analytical and reflective)	5	8.62	7	12.06
Sufficient (creatively productive)	8	13.79	25	43.10
Average (activity search)	24	41.37	23	39.65
Low (passive)	21	36.2	3	5.17

Table 2

The results of the experimental investigation for the forming singing skills in the preschoolers (163 children)

Levels	KG	KG	EG	EG
	number	%	number	%
High (topical and presentative)	6	8.1	9	10.11
Sufficient (creatively productive)	11	14.86	51	57.3
Average (activity search)	40	54.05	16	17.97
Low (passive)	17	22.97	13	14.6

Table 3

The results of the experimental investigation for the forming singing skills and the development of the singing reflection in primary link pupils (116 children)

Levels	KG	KG	EG	EG
	number	%	number	%
High (analytical and reflective)	11	9.55	16	13.76
Sufficient (creatively productive)	19	17.06	76	68.0
Average (activity search)	64	58.18	39	31.65
Low (passive)	38	32.9	16	15.04

The main principle of the forming singing skills of the pupils of junior school age is the principle of continuity. Based on the components of the continuity, we have developed questionnaires and tests for study of the levels of formation this phenomenon. Thanks to them, we were able to identify gaps in the area of the education.

Conclusions of investigation and the perspectives the further scientific investigations. As a result of the molding experiment, we discovered that significant development of singing reflection was observed in pupils of the third and fourth forms. The outlined phenomenon is connected with the deepening and the expansion of knowledge and the skills in comparison with the pupils of the first and second forms. During the experimental research we found that preschoolers are not able to evaluate independently their own singing yet. Because they haven't the experience. We have determined that this phenomenon is a newborn in the children of 6 years of age.

The collectives of the experimental and the control groups were happy to fulfill the training tasks, the music teachers of the institutions of general secondary education provided the assistance in creating a good positive microclimate in the classes, and continued to work out our practical tasks for singing, interviewing, questioning, testing and questioning. The music teachers in the work with the EG were to able observe a high interest to performing vocal exercises «singing in the drawings», the songs, some exercises from the course of video tutorials on the Internet portal «YouTube», increased emotional the attitude to singing activity.

It should be noted that the principle of continuity, the methods and the methodical approach «singing in the drawings» requires further introduction into the institutions of secondary general and preschool education.

The principle of the continuity requires the development of the crosscutting programs, the training materials, the textbook, manuals. The scientific principle of continuity requires a detailed study by the scientists and of introduction in the educational process of the institutions of preschool education and the primary link of secondary general education.

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Велігура О. О.

ORCID ID <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-3904-664X>

Викладач-методист по класу фортепіано та сольного співу
Комунального закладу «Семенівська дитяча музична школа»

Чернігівської області

(Семенівка, Україна) E-mail: helen.ve1983@gmail.com

ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ МЕТОДИКИ ФОРМУВАННЯ СПІВАЦЬКИХ НАВИЧОК ДІТЕЙ МОЛОДШОГО ШКІЛЬНОГО ВІКУ І ДОШКІЛЬНИКІВ ЗА ПРИНЦИПОМ НАСТУПНОСТІ

Стаття присвячена проблемі наступності у формуванні співацьких навичок дітей молодшого шкільного віку та дошкільників. Визначено, що формування співацького потенціалу учнів початкової ланки зароджується у дошкільному віці і отримує подальшу реалізацію у молодшому шкільному віці. У цьому контексті актуальність має забезпечення педагогічних умов, методів, методичних прийомів та елементів навчання для запровадження поступової лінії розвитку співацьких навичок на основі принципу наступності.

У статті представлено апробовані методи з формування дослідженого феномену дітей окресленої вікової категорії та результати формувального експерименту, що мав три етапи: цілепокладання, мобілізуючий та узагальнюючий і відбувався на базі Закладу дошкільної освіти №6 «Сонечко» Семенівської міської ради Чернігівської області та Семенівської гімназії №2 Семенівської районної ради Чернігівської області.

Метою роботи є розробка, теоретичне обґрунтування та експериментальне тестування методів формування співацьких навичок дітей молодшого шкільного віку і дошкільників, з урахуванням принципу наступності та результатів визначення стану цього явища.

Методологія. Методологічною базою дослідження стали: державний документ «Національна стратегія розвитку освіти в Україні на 2012-2021 рр», провідні аспекти методики вокалу та хорової роботи з дітьми (О. Апраксина, О. Борисова, К. Малініна); основні положення особливостей структури дитячого вокального апарату (П. Гонтаренко, Л. Дмитрієв, Ю. Юцевич, В. Юшманов); основні принципи вікових специфічних особливостей розвитку психіки дошкільнят (О. Кононко, В. Кузьменко) і дітей молодшого шкільного віку (Л. Венгер, М. Заброцький, В. Кузьменко, В. Кутішенко). У науковому дослідженні нами було використано наступні методи: пояснювально-ілюстративний, інформаційно-рецептивний, евристичний; методи для встановлення рівнів розвиненості рефлексії співу (інтерв'ювання, тестування, анкетування, опитування).

Наукова новизна полягає у: вперше розглянуто проблему наступності у формуванні співацьких навичок учнів початкової ланки закладів загальної середньої освіти і дошкільників; зроблено інтегровані методи в напрямку; була розроблена інтегрована покрокова методологія з наміченого напрямку; створено комплекс практичних завдань, серед яких обов'язковим є методичний прийом «спів по малюнках» з метою вивчення стану формування співацьких навичок учнів 1-4 класів і дошкільників; нами також розроблені тестові завдання, анкети для визначення рівня розвитку рефлексії співу учнів початкової ланки закладів загальної середньої освіти; введено у науковий обіг поняття «співацька рефлексія».

Висновки. У результаті проведення формувального експерименту ми відзначили, що в учнів третього і четвертого класів спостерігається суттєвий розвиток рефлексії співу. Окреслене явище пов'язане з поглибленням і розширенням знань і навичок у порівнянні з учнями першого і другого класів. Під час експериментального дослідження ми виявили, що дошкільники ще не здатні оцінювати свій власний спів, оскільки не мають досвіду. Зазначений феномен є новоутворенням у дітей шестирічного віку.

Ключові слова: наступність, співацькі навички, рефлексія співу.

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Рецензент: доктор педагогічних наук, професор С. С. Горбенко